

RIVEAL PROJECT

RIPARIAN FOREST VALUES AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES – RIPARIAN CARBON

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RIPARIAN CARBON IS....

... the amount of carbon that has been sequestered from the atmosphere and is now stored within the riparian ecosystem, mainly within the living biomass and soil, and to a lesser extent in dead wood and litter.

Riparian carbon storage varies along environmental gradients and for different riparian species. In addition to climate, several local factors may influence the carbon storage capacity of riparian ecosystems like the floodplain width, the gradient of inundation, the valley geometry, the channel morphology and the flow regime.

Riparian carbon is stored in three different pools:

- A. **Aboveground biomass** (AGB), including all living trees, shrubs and herbaceous vegetation
- B. **Belowground biomass** (BGB) which includes the root system
- C. **Carbon stored in the mineral and organic soil layer** including litter, deadwood and woody debris

Field view of the AGB (a) and soil (b) riparian carbon pools in a small-sized tributary of Tagus River.

Riparian zone dominated by alders.

WHY IS IT SO IMPORTANT?

Riparian forests have been referred as important carbon sinks; thus, they are crucial systems to mitigate the effects of climate change and to provide a regulation Ecosystem Service.

Riparian forests are subjected to frequent floods and influenced by geomorphologic processes, exhibit high spatial and temporal variability with consequent high potential for long-term carbon storage.

FIELD SAMPLING

Tree inventory

- Sampling design and selection of the plots for inventory; GPS location
- Inventory of all trees inside the plots: diameter at breast height (DBH), total height, azimuth, and distance to the plot centre
- Application of the allometric biomass models available in the literature
- Development of new biomass equations in case no models are available using destructive sampling and field data

Destructive sampling (above photo), weighing (below photo) and a schematic example of a circular plot with mapping of individual canopies of two species (black and red circles) (Data published in: Fernandes et al., 2020; doi:10.3390/f11040376).

Shrub and herbaceous sampling

- Collection of all understory plant biomass aboveground within 50 cm x 50 cm plots
- Assessments of the weighing in the field and determination of the dry weight in the laboratory

Collection of herbaceous material.

Soil sampling

- Organic soil layer: collection of partially decomposed material at the soil surface
- Mineral soil layer: collection of soil samples up to 30 cm depth with a soil probe, also soil bulk density for converting organic material in carbon

Collection of organic (above) and mineral soil layer (below).

RIPARIAN CARBON IN RIVEAL

Field sampling was performed in Alva and Lima rivers to obtain tree inventory data, namely for the dominant woody species and the respective DBH average by dominant species (*Alnus glutinosa*, *Salix salviifolia*, *Fraxinus angustifolia*, *Salix atrocinerea* and *Acacia dealbata*).

Touvedo – Lima River

Fronhas- Alva River

Location map showing Portugal and the river landscape of the two case studies downstream of the Touvedo, a run-of-river dam, and Fronhas, a reservoir storage dam.

Carbon stocks will be estimated for the riparian zone and adjacent land-uses in both rivers, before and after regulation.

